

Impact of Non-stellar Sources on the Intergalactic Medium: Tests with Lyman- α Forest Statistics

Arghyadeep Basu,^{1*} Benedetta Ciardi,^{1†} James S. Bolton,² Matteo Viel,³ et al.

¹Max-planck-Institut für Astrophysik, Karl-Schwarzschild-Strasse 1, D-85741, Garching, Germany

Accepted XXX. Received YYY; in original form ZZZ

ABSTRACT

Key words:

1 INTRODUCTION

The growth of primordial density fluctuation from gravitational instabilities gave rise to the formation of the first stars and galaxies, which started to emit photons with enough energy to ionize the surrounding intergalactic medium (IGM) and initiate the last global phase transition of universe, namely the Epoch of Reionization (EoR; [Loeb & Barkana 2001](#)). Observations of high- z QSO absorption spectra ([Fan et al. 2003](#); [Fan et al. 2006a](#); [Gunn & Peterson 1965](#); [McGreer et al. 2015](#); [Bosman et al. 2018](#); [Davies et al. 2018](#); [Bosman et al. 2022](#)) and Lyman- α emitters (LAEs; [Pentericci et al. 2014](#); [Tilvi et al. 2014](#); [De Barros et al. 2017](#); [Mason et al. 2018](#)), of the IGM thermal properties ([Bolton et al. 2012](#); [Raskutti et al. 2012](#)), and of the Thompson scattering optical depth ([Komatsu et al. 2011](#)) indicate that reionization is an extending process which is believed to be largely complete by $z \sim 5.5$, although patches of neutral hydrogen are found also at lower redshift

These abundance of observations is accompanied by an increasingly sophisticated modeling of the reionization process employing a variety of approaches, ranging from semi-analytic and semi-numeric models, to full radiation hydrodynamic simulations. Although in most literature galaxies are thought to be the main drivers of reionization (e.g. [Becker & Bolton 2013](#); [Bouwens et al. 2015](#); [Robertson et al. 2015](#); [Madau 2017](#); [Dayal et al. 2020](#); [Eide et al. 2018](#); [Eide et al. 2020](#); [Trebtsch et al. 2021](#); [Kannan et al. 2021](#)), it is still unclear which are the properties of those contributing the most (e.g. small vs. massive galaxies; [Naidu et al. 2020, 2021](#); [Matthee et al. 2022](#)). Additionally, the recent detection of a larger than expected number density of faint quasars at intermediate (i.e. $z \sim 4$; [Giallongo et al. 2015, 2019](#); [Boutsia et al. 2018](#)) and high (i.e. $z > 6$; [Weigel et al. 2015](#); [McGreer et al. 2018](#); [Parsa et al. 2018](#); [Akiyama et al. 2018](#)) redshift, have renewed the interest in quasars as possible strong contributors to the ionization budget.

Whatever the main source of ionizing photons is, the physical properties of the IGM in terms of ionization and thermal state are influenced by a variety of sources, including the above mentioned stars and quasars, but also X-ray binaries (XRBs; [Mirabel et al. 2011](#);

[Fragos et al. 2013b,a](#); [Madau & Fragos 2017](#); [Sazonov & Khabibullin 2017](#); [Mineo et al. \(2012a,b\)](#)), Bremsstrahlung emission from shock heated interstellar medium (ISM; [Fabbiano 1989](#), [Chevalier & Clegg 1985](#), [Pacucci et al. 2014](#), [Suchkov et al. 1994](#), [Strickland & Stevens 2000](#)), low energy cosmic rays ([Ginzburg & Ozernoi 1966](#); [Nath & Biermann 1993](#); [Sazonov & Sunyaev 2015](#); [Leite et al. 2017](#)), self-annihilation or decay of dark matter (e.g. [Liu et al. 2016](#)) and plasma beam instabilities in TeV blazars (e.g. [Chang et al. 2012](#); [Puchwein et al. 2012](#)). As discussed in [Eide et al. \(2018\)](#) and [Eide et al. \(2020\)](#), the more energetic sources are responsible for the partially ionized and warm gas found outside of the regions fully ionized by stars. Additionally, they can also slightly increase the IGM temperature in comparison to the one obtained in star driven reionization scenarios.

Their impact on studies of the 21cm signal from neutral hydrogen at high- z has been widely recognized and investigated. In principle, one could also expect an impact on the Lyman- α ($Ly\alpha$) forest in terms of broadening of the thermal widths, with the consequence of increasing the transmission flux. In this work we investigate the impact of sources other than stars on statistical studies of the Lyman- α forest by running tailored radiative transfer simulations of the reionization process. The structure of the paper is as follows. In Section 2 we introduce the hydrodynamic and radiative transfer simulations employed; in Section 3 we discuss our results, and in Section 4 we give our conclusions.

2 METHODOLOGY

Here, we describe how we have post-processed the outputs of a hydrodynamical simulation (Section 2.1) with the multi-frequency radiative transfer (RT) code CRASH (Section 2.2) to obtain a suite of simulations of reionization (Section 2.3).

2.1 The cosmological hydrodynamic simulation

To obtain the gas and source distribution and properties, we have used outputs at $z=5.16-15$ from a Sherwood-type hydrodynamical simulation performed in a comoving cubic box of size $20 h^{-1}$ Mpc ([Bolton et al. 2016](#)), with the parallel Tree-PM smoothed particle

* E-mail: basu@mpa-garching.mpg.de

† E-mail: ciardi@mpa-garching.mpg.de

hydrodynamics (SPH) code p-GADGET-3, which is an updated version of GADGET-2 (Springel 2005; Springel et al. 2001). The box contains 2×1024^3 gas and dark matter particles, each of mass $m_{\text{gas}} = 9.97 \times 10^6 M_{\odot}$ and $m_{\text{DM}} = 5.37 \times 10^7 M_{\odot}$, respectively. Haloes are identified using the friends-of-friends algorithm with a linking length of 0.2 times the mean inter-particle separation. The gravitational softening length for the simulation is set to 1/30th of the mean linear interparticle spacing, and star formation is incorporated using a simple and computationally efficient prescription which converts all gas particles with overdensity $\Delta > 10^3$ and temperature $T < 10^5 \text{K}$ into collisionless stars (Viel et al. 2004, 2013). Note that because of this simple treatment our simulation does not self-consistently model star formation and feedback, but is perfectly appropriate to investigate IGM properties. The Sherwood model adopts a Planck 2013 consistent cosmology (Planck Collaboration et al. 2014) with $\Omega_{\text{m}} = 0.308$, $\Omega_{\Lambda} = 0.692$, $\Omega_{\text{b}} = 0.0482$, $\sigma_8 = 0.829$, $n_{\text{s}} = 0.963$, $h = 0.678$, where the symbols have their usual meaning. Throughout the paper, the gas is assumed to be of primordial composition with a hydrogen and helium number fraction of 0.92 and 0.08, respectively, and no metals.

2.2 The radiative transfer code CRASH

The radiative transfer of ionizing photons through the IGM is implemented by post-processing the outputs of the hydrodynamic simulation using the code 3D non-equilibrium and multi-frequency code CRASH (e.g. Ciardi et al. 2001; Maselli et al. 2003, 2009; Graziani et al. 2013; Hariharan et al. 2017; Glatzle et al. 2019, 2022). The code evaluates self-consistently the ionization states of hydrogen and helium, as well as the evolution of gas temperature. CRASH employs a Monte Carlo-based ray tracing approach, where the propagation of ionizing radiation is represented by multi-frequency photon packets that dynamically trace the spatial and temporal distribution of radiation within the simulation volume. The version of CRASH employed here has a comprehensive treatment of UV and soft X-ray photons, including X-ray ionization, heating, and secondary electron interactions (Graziani et al. 2018). For an in-depth understanding of CRASH, we encourage readers to refer to the foundational papers.

2.3 The radiative transfer simulation of reionization

To use the hydrodynamical simulation outputs in the RT code CRASH, we have gridded the gas density and temperature extracted from the snapshots onto N_{grid}^3 cells. More specifically, the RT is performed with $N_{\text{grid}} = 128$ (corresponding to a spatial resolution of $156 h^{-1} \text{ckpc}$) in the range $z = 15 - 8$, while at $z < 8$ the resolution is increased to $N_{\text{grid}} = 256$ (corresponding to $78 h^{-1} \text{ckpc}$) to ensure a better description of the Lyman- α forest related statistics. The gridded properties of the gas are obtained by assigning the particle data to a regular grid using the SPH kernel (Monaghan 1992), while the corresponding grid for the halo masses and positions is obtained by using the cloud-in-cell and friends-of-friends algorithms (Hockney & Eastwood 1988). If more halos end up in the same cell, their masses are combined.

For each output i at z_i of the hydro-dynamical simulation, the RT is followed for a time $t_{\text{H}}(z_{i+1}) - t_{\text{H}}(z_i)$, where $t_{\text{H}}(z_i)$ is the Hubble time corresponding to z_i . In order to account for the expansion of the Universe between the i -th and $(i + 1)$ -th snapshots, the gas number density is evolved as $n(\mathbf{x}, z) = n(\mathbf{x}, z_i)(1 + z)^3/(1 + z_i)^3$, where $\mathbf{x} \equiv (x_c, y_c, z_c)$ are the coordinates of each cell c . To avoid accounting twice for the UV background (which is included in the

Figure 1. Redshift evolution of the HI photo-ionization rate adopted in this work (solid red line), together with the commonly adopted (dashed grey) and a compilation of observational data.

hydrodynamic simulations), at $z \leq 9$ all cells with $T < 10^5 \text{K}$ are assigned a temperature $T_{i+1} = T_i(1 + z_{i+1}^2)/(1 + z_i^2)$, i.e. only the effect of the adiabatic cooling since the previous snapshot is taken into account in the evolution of the temperature, while the photoheating due to the UVB is discarded. For the cells with $T \geq 10^5 \text{K}$, the value of the temperature is not changed to take into account the heating from shocks, which cannot be captured by the RT. The ionization fractions are initialized to their expected residual values from the recombination epoch i.e. $x_{\text{HII}} = 10^{-4}$ and $x_{\text{HeII}} = x_{\text{HeIII}} = 0$.

The source emissivity is evaluated according to the prescription introduced by Ciardi et al. (2012), namely, we have assumed a total comoving hydrogen ionizing emissivity at each redshift, $\epsilon_{\text{tot}}(z_i)$, and distributed it in terms of rate of ionizing photons among all the halos proportionally to their mass. This approach assures by design that the emissivity is broadly consistent with $z \sim 5 - 6$ observations (Fan et al. 2006b; Glikman et al. 2011; Calverley et al. 2011; Bolton et al. 2012; Becker et al. 2015b; Giallongo et al. 2015). Additionally, it does not require any assumption on the escape fraction of ionizing photons, which is a very uncertain parameter (Wood & Loeb 2000; Dayal & Ferrara 2018). Differently from Ciardi et al. (2012), though, rather than having a purely linear relation between the ionizing emissivity and the halo mass, we have incorporated a Gaussian noise with mean $\mu = 0$ and standard deviation $\sigma = 0.01$ in the log-log scale conserving the total ionizing emissivity (as done in Garaldi et al. 2019). In Fig. 1 we show the resulting evolution of photo-ionization rate, together with a compilation of observational data.

To reduce the large number of sources present in the simulation box and thus the computational time, we have adopted the source clustering technique developed by Eide et al. (2020) with a luminosity limit of 0.1 and maximum radius of $\sqrt{2} \times 2.01$ (see the original paper for more details). Every ionizing source emits 10^4 photon packets which are lost once they exit the simulation box, i.e. no periodic boundary condition has been used.

The spectral energy distribution (SED) of the sources has been

Figure 2. Globally averaged spectral energy distributions (SEDs) $\bar{S}(\nu, z)$ adopted in different simulations with sources as : single stars only (SS, solid black curve); combination of single stars, ISM and XRBs (SS+ISM+XRBs, dotted black curve) and combination of binary stars, ISM and XRBs (BS+ISM+XRBs, dashed black curve). The faint vertical gray lines indicate the ionization thresholds for neutral hydrogen (13.6 eV), neutral helium (24.6 eV) and singly ionized helium (54.4 eV). Different colors indicate different redshifts.

derived following Eide et al. (2018), Eide et al. (2020), and Ma et al. (2022), which include the contribution from single (SS) and binary (BS) stars, XRBs and thermal Bremsstrahlung from supernova-heated ISM. While we refer the reader to the original papers for more details, here we note that stars dominate the total SED budget at energy $h_p \nu \leq 60$ eV, while the ISM contribution is dominant above the HeII ionization threshold into hard UV and the soft X-rays (i.e. in the range $h_p \nu \in [60, 500]$ eV), and the XRBs start to contribute at $h_p \nu > 500$ eV (see figure 2 in Eide et al. 2018 and figure 1 in Ma et al. 2022 for a visual inspection). For all RT simulations, the spectra of ionizing sources extend to a maximum frequency of ~ 2 keV and are discretized into 82 frequency bins, with bins more densely spaced around the ionization thresholds of hydrogen (13.6 eV) and helium (24.6 eV and 54.4 eV). We run three simulations: one with ionizing sources consisting solely of single stars (SS), another adding also the contribution from the ISM and XRBs (SS+ISM+XRBs), and a third that includes binary stars along with the ISM and XRBs (BS+ISM+XRBs). The resulting SEDs for all three simulations are shown in Figure 2.

3 RESULTS

The central question we aim to address here is: *which is the impact of non-stellar sources on the properties of the IGM described by the Ly α forest?* We will first discuss qualitative differences, then present the resulting reionization and thermal histories, and finally we will examine the impact on the observable quantities associated to the Ly α forest.

3.1 Qualitative Overview

For a qualitative discussion of the results, in figure 3 we show maps of the IGM ionization and thermal state at $z = 6$, which reflect what

Figure 3. From top to bottom, slice maps of the H II, He II, He III fractions and IGM temperature at $z \sim 6$ for different combinations of ionizing sources: single stars (SS, first column); single stars, ISM and XRBs (SS+ISM+XRBs, second), and binary stars, ISM and XRBs (BS+ISM+XRBs, third). The lower sets of rows show the difference with respect to the simulations with single stars only. The maps are $20h^{-1}\text{cMpc}$ wide and $78h^{-1}\text{ckpc}$ thick.

already discussed at higher redshift in [Eide et al. \(2018\)](#), [Eide et al. \(2020\)](#) and [Ma et al. \(2022\)](#). The slices have a width of $20h^{-1}\text{cMpc}$ and are $78h^{-1}\text{ckpc}$ thick. The gas in SS is either fully ionized and hot (i.e. $x_{\text{HII}} \approx x_{\text{HeII}} \approx 1$, $T_{\text{IGM}} \gtrsim 10^4\text{ K}$) or neutral and cold (i.e. $x_{\text{HII}} \approx x_{\text{HeII}} \lesssim 10^{-4}$, $T_{\text{IGM}} \sim 10\text{ K}$). In SS+ISM+XRBS, instead, the neutral gas has been heated and partially ionized by the higher energy photons emitted by the more energetic sources. The additional heating ($\sim 100\text{ K}$) and ionization can be clearly seen in the difference maps as red pixels. There we also see that in the fully ionized regions x_{HeII} is slightly lower (blue pixels) than in the SS simulation because it has been ionized to He III. This is also accompanied by a slightly higher temperature¹.

The inclusion of binary stars provides further differences in the ionization and thermal state of the IGM. Due to the larger number of ionizing photons produced by binary stars, the extent of the fully ionized H II regions is larger compared to simulations with single stars. As binary stars also emit a non negligible amount of photons above the ionization level of He sc ii, we observe a small impact on the Helium content and the gas temperature. Effectively, the simulation BS+ISM+XRBS produces less He III fraction compared to SS+ISM+XRBS due to the fact that, majority of the ionizing photons are already used in extending the ionized bubbles and the total number of ionizing photons in the entire simulation volume is constant at each time step.

3.2 Reionization history

To discuss the overall effect induced by different source types, in figure 4 we display the redshift evolution of the volume averaged neutral H I fraction for all simulations, together with the fractional difference with respect to SS, and a compilation of observational results. By design, all simulations are consistent with observational constraints at $z \sim 5.8$, where our primary focus lies. The curves are also able to reproduce most data points also at higher redshift, although here there less consistency among different observations.

As our main goal is to investigate the impact of different choices of the sources SEDs, in the bottom panel of the figure we display the fractional difference with respect to the SS simulation. As discussed in the previous section, the inclusion of BS and/or more energetic sources results in more ionization, and this results in a lower H I fraction, with a maximum difference at $z \sim 5.6$ of $\sim 7.5\%$ and 10% , in the SS+ISM+XRBS and BS+ISM+XRBS case, respectively. As reionization progresses and $\langle x_{\text{HII}} \rangle$ drops below 10^{-4} , the differences among the various simulations decrease, eventually approaching zero. However, the simulation with binary stars retain a higher amount of H I in comparison to those with only single stars, primarily because some of the cells ionized earlier have had time to recombine.

3.3 Thermal history

The ionization of hydrogen and helium injects energy into the IGM through photo-heating, raising its temperature, and consequently affecting the dynamics of gas, its cooling rate, and its accretion onto galaxies. In Figure 5 we show the redshift evolution of the IGM temperature at mean density, calculated by selecting all the cells in the simulation volume with gas density within 1% of the mean one.

¹ We note that the alternating blue and red pixels in the fully ionized region are due to Monte-Carlo noise, as it is statistically impossible for two cells with $x_{\text{HII}} = 1$ to have exactly the same temperature in simulations with different source types.

Figure 4. *Top panel:* Redshift evolution of the volume averaged x_{HII} for SS (solid red curve), SS+ISM+XRBS (dotted blue) and BS+ISM+XRBS (dashed green). The symbols denote a compilation of observational constraints from literature ([Bosman et al. 2022](#); [Fan et al. 2006b](#); [Davies et al. 2018](#); [Mason et al. 2018](#); [McGreer et al. 2018](#); [Greig et al. 2017, 2019](#); [Hoag et al. 2019](#); [Yang et al. 2020](#); [Umeda et al. 2024](#); [Đurovčíková et al. 2024](#); [Nakane et al. 2024](#); [Spina et al. 2024](#); [Zhu et al. 2024](#)). *Bottom panel:* Fractional difference with respect to SS.

As expected, T_0 rises with decreasing redshift, reaching a peak of $\sim 13,500\text{ K}$ at $z \sim 6$, when about 99% of the simulation volume is ionized. Subsequently, the rate of heat injection from photo-heating diminishes, leading to a plateau followed by a gradual decline in temperature. Interestingly, this decline is much shallower than what is suggested a compilation of relevant observations ([Bolton et al. 2012](#); [Boera et al. 2019](#); [Gaikwad et al. 2020](#))². The shallower evolution is likely due to additional heating from double helium reionization or the extended duration of the reionization process.

Although the general trend of all curves is the same, there are some differences, more clearly visible in the bottom panel of Figure 5, where we show the fractional temperature difference with respect to the simulation with single stars only. Both SS+ISM+XRBS and BS+ISM+XRBS have a higher temperature because of the extra heating injected by the more energetic photons, with the binary stars producing even higher values. The maximum differences, though, are of $\sim 5\%$ at $z \sim 8$, and reduces to $\sim 1\%$ at lower redshift, towards the end of reionization. At $z \sim 5$ the SS+ISM+XRBS and BS+ISM+XRBS simulations have converged, primarily because the presence of binary stars leads to more rapid ionization and photo-heating, allowing

² We note that we have not shown observations from [Schaye et al. \(2000\)](#); [Lidz et al. \(2010\)](#); [Becker et al. \(2010\)](#); [Garzilli et al. \(2012\)](#); [Boera et al. \(2014\)](#); [Rorai et al. \(2017\)](#); [Hiss et al. \(2018\)](#); [Walther et al. \(2019\)](#); [Gaikwad et al. \(2021\)](#) which are mostly at $z < 5$ where we do not have any output from our simulations.

Figure 5. *Top panel:* Redshift evolution of IGM temperature at mean density (T_0) for SS (solid red curve), SS+ISM+XRBS (dotted blue) and BS+ISM+XRBS (dashed green). The symbols denote the compilation of observational constraints from the literature (Bolton et al. 2012; Boera et al. 2019; Gaikwad et al. 2020). *Bottom panel:* Fractional difference with respect to SS.

enough time for cooling, while T_0 in the SS+ISM+XRBS simulation continues to rise and eventually matches the temperature in the binary star simulation.

In the following we will investigate if the differences in IGM temperature affect the Lyman- α forest properties.

3.4 Ly α forest statistics

To compare Ly α forest properties, we have generated synthetic spectra by extracting 4096 sightlines at each RT snapshot, each spanning the full box length parallel to the z -direction. For each pixel i in a sightline we evaluate the normalized transmission flux $F(i) = \exp[-\tau(i)]$, where

$$\tau(i) = \frac{c\sigma_\alpha\delta R}{\sqrt{\pi}} \sum_{j=1}^N n_{\text{HI}}(j) \tilde{V}(i, j) \quad (1)$$

is the Ly α optical depth. Here N is the number of pixels in a sightline, σ_α is the Ly α scattering cross-section, c is the speed of light, δR is the size of a pixel in proper distance units, $n_{\text{HI}}(j)$ is the H I number density at the position of pixel j , and \tilde{V} is the convoluted Voigt profile approximation provided by Tepper-García (2006). The latter depends on the IGM temperature and the peculiar velocity. Throughout this paper, we ignore the contamination from other lines into the wavelength window of the Ly α forest, and notice that this is not expected to have any impact on our results.

Figure 6. IGM properties along a reference line of sight at $z = 6$ for SS (solid red curve), SS+ISM+XRBS (dotted blue) and BS+ISM+XRBS (dashed green). From top to bottom the panels refer to the H I fraction, H I number density, IGM temperature, Ly α optical depth, and normalized transmission flux. Colors of the curves denote the features in different simulations as discussed in previous figures.

3.4.1 Individual lines of sight

As a reference, in Figure 6 we display the neutral hydrogen fraction (x_{HI}), the H I number density (n_{HI}), the IGM gas temperature (T_{IGM}), the optical depth (τ), and the transmitted flux (F) along a single line of sight (LOS) at $z \sim 6$. For clarity, we omit the pixel index when referring to the values of these physical quantities. Along the LOS, we observe both fully neutral and almost completely ionized (with $x_{\text{HI}} \sim 10^{-5} - 10^{-4}$ and $n_{\text{HI}} \sim 10^{-10} - 10^{-8} \text{ cm}^{-3}$) regions, reflecting the ongoing reionization process. The abundance of HI is very similar in all simulations, with a slightly higher value in the SS, reflecting what already discussed in the previous sections. While the ionized regions are characterized by $T_{\text{IGM}} \sim 10^4$ K, in the others the temperature corresponds either to the one of a fully neutral gas adiabatically expanded and cooled (in the SS simulations) or to a gas heated between a few hundreds and a few thousands K by the more energetic photons present in SS+ISM+XRBS and BS+ISM+XRBS. The differences between the ionized and neutral regions are reflected also in the corresponding Ly α optical depth, with values ranging from below 10 to more than 10^5 . The lower τ values correspond to small spikes in the transmitted flux, indicating limited transmission through these regions. As we shift to a lower redshift, $z \sim 5$, the IGM shows significant evolution. The simulation volume becomes predominantly ionized, with the vast majority of cells along the sightline showing n_{HI} values well below 10^{-8} cm^{-3} . The ionized cells are also much hotter, with temperatures frequently exceeding 10^4 K. This increased temperature leads to a more uniform and lower optical depth across

Figure 7. *Top panel:* Redshift evolution of mean transmission flux for SS (solid red curve), SS+ISM+XRBS (dotted blue) and BS+ISM+XRBS (dashed green), together with a compilation of observational data from high- z quasar spectra (Becker et al. 2015a; Eilers et al. 2018; Bosman et al. 2018; Bosman et al. 2022). *Bottom panel:* Fractional difference with respect to SS.

the sightline, resulting in a greater fraction of the transmitted flux and larger regions where the flux is clearly visible. The differences in F are negligible as the optical depth is generally high enough to ensure minimal transmission, making any deviations in τ less impactful on the overall flux.

While the characteristics discussed above are common to the majority of LOSs, to provide a more quantitative comparison in the next sections we calculate quantities which more accurately capture the statistical behaviour of the Ly α forest.

3.4.2 Evolution of the mean transmission flux

In figure 7 we plot the redshift evolution of the average normalised transmitted flux, $\langle F \rangle$, for our three models. All curves show the expected rapid increase at $z < 6.5$, and reproduce quite well the available observational data, especially at $z < 5.8$. Although all models give similar results (with differences of $\sim 4\%$ at $z \sim 6.5$, decreasing to less than 1% at $z \sim 5$), the flux transmitted in simulations with more energetic sources is typically larger than in SS, reflecting the production of larger gas temperature and ionization fraction. Similarly, in the final stages of reionization, the presence of BS reduces the transmitted flux due to the slightly higher values of neutral hydrogen obtained (see figure 4).

3.4.3 Evolution of the effective optical depth

3.4.4 1-D Flux Power Spectra

As one of the most important statistical quantities relevant to Ly α forest studies, we compute the 1-D flux power spectra by analyzing all

Figure 8. *Top panel:* Redshift evolution of Lyman- α effective optical depth for SS (solid red curve), SS+ISM+XRBS (dotted blue) and BS+ISM+XRBS (dashed green), together with a compilation of observational data from high- z quasar spectra (Becker et al. 2015a; Bosman et al. 2018; Bosman et al. 2022; Yang et al. 2020). *Bottom panel:* Fractional difference with respect to SS.

sightlines extracted from the simulation volume. Figure 9 displays the dimensionless Ly α forest transmission power spectra at $z \sim 6$ and $z \sim 5$, where the flux F has been scaled to match the observed transmission flux from Bosman et al. (2022). The shape of the power spectra at $z \sim 6$ and 5 is similar, increasing from $k \sim 10^{-0.5} \text{ s km}^{-1}$ until $k \sim 10^{-1.6} \text{ s km}^{-1}$, the characteristic scale of fluctuations in the Ly α forest. At larger scales the power decreases. Despite the similar trend, the power at $z \sim 5$ is much smaller because the IGM is almost fully ionized and thus the transmission flux is nearly uniform across all sightlines. The slight slope observed at the highest k -values is mainly due to the limitations in spatial resolution of the simulations, which can affect the accuracy of the power spectrum at smaller scales.

We comparing the various simulations, we observe that at $z \sim 6$ the inclusion of more energetic sources in SS+ISM+XRBS increases the power spectrum by $\sim 5\%$ at $k \sim 10^{-1.6} \text{ s km}^{-1}$, while such differences vanish at the smallest/largest scales probed by the simulations. The differences are slightly smaller in SS+ISM+XRBS, and the peak in bottom panel is shifted to larger physical scales. The major contribution to these deviations up to the peak is primarily due to fluctuations in the neutral hydrogen (H I) fractions. As k increases further, particularly beyond $k \gtrsim 0.1$, the deviations approach near zero or even become negative in the simulation with binary stars. At these higher k -values, the primary reason is line broadening due to increased temperatures, though fluctuations in the ionization state also contribute to the observed effects.

Figure 9. 1D dimensionless Ly α forest transmission flux power spectra at $z = 6$ (upper figure) and 5 (lower) for SS (solid red curve), SS+ISM+XRBs (dotted blue) and BS+ISM+XRBs (dashed green). The bottom panels display the fractional difference with respect to SS.

4 CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

All simulations were carried out on the machines of Max Planck Institute for Astrophysics (MPA) and Max Planck Computing and Data Facility (MPCDF). AB thanks the entire EoR research group of MPA for all the encouraging comments for this project. This work made extensive use of publicly available software packages : `numpy` (van der Walt et al. 2011), `matplotlib` (Hunter 2007), `scipy`

(Jones et al. 2001) and `CoReCon` (Garaldi 2023). Authors thank the developers of these packages.

DATA AVAILABILITY

The data used for this study is available from the p-sherwood simulation suite mentored by James Bolton. The final data products from this study will be shared on reasonable request to the corresponding author.

REFERENCES

- Akiyama M., et al., 2018, *PASJ*, **70**, S34
 Becker G. D., Bolton J. S., 2013, *MNRAS*, **436**, 1023
 Becker G. D., Bolton J. S., Haehnelt M. G., Sargent W. L. W., 2010, *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society*, **410**, 1096–1112
 Becker G. D., Bolton J. S., Lidz A., 2015a, *Publ. Astron. Soc. Australia*, **32**, e045
 Becker G. D., Bolton J. S., Madau P., Pettini M., Ryan-Weber E. V., Venemans B. P., 2015b, *MNRAS*, **447**, 3402
 Boera E., Murphy M. T., Becker G. D., Bolton J. S., 2014, *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society*, **441**, 1916–1933
 Boera E., Becker G. D., Bolton J. S., Nasir F., 2019, *ApJ*, **872**, 101
 Bolton J. S., Becker G. D., Raskutti S., Wyithe J. S. B., Haehnelt M. G., Sargent W. L. W., 2012, *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society*, **419**, 2880
 Bolton J. S., Puchwein E., Sijacki D., Haehnelt M. G., Kim T.-S., Meiksin A., Regan J. A., Viel M., 2016, *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society*, **464**, 897
 Bosman S. E. I., Fan X., Jiang L., Reed S., Matsuoka Y., Becker G., Haehnelt M., 2018, *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society*
 Bosman S. E. I., et al., 2022, *MNRAS*, **514**, 55
 Boutsia K., Grazian A., Giallongo E., Fiore F., Civano F., 2018, *ApJ*, **869**, 20
 Bouwens R. J., Illingworth G. D., Oesch P. A., Caruana J., Holwerda B., Smit R., Wilkins S., 2015, *The Astrophysical Journal*, **811**, 140
 Calverley A. P., Becker G. D., Haehnelt M. G., Bolton J. S., 2011, *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society*, **412**, 2543
 Ciardi B., Ferrara A., Marri S., Raimondo G., 2001, *MNRAS*, **324**, 381
 Ciardi B., Bolton J. S., Maselli A., Graziani L., 2012, *MNRAS*, **423**, 558
 Davies F. B., Hennawi J. F., Eilers A.-C., Lukić Z., 2018, *The Astrophysical Journal*, **855**, 106
 Dayal P., Ferrara A., 2018, *Phys. Rep.*, **780**, 1
 Dayal P., et al., 2020, *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society*, **495**, 3065–3078
 De Barros S., et al., 2017, *A&A*, **608**, A123
 Eide M. B., Graziani L., Ciardi B., Feng Y., Kakiichi K., Di Matteo T., 2018, *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society*, **476**, 1174–1190
 Eide M. B., Ciardi B., Graziani L., Busch P., Feng Y., Di Matteo T., 2020, *MNRAS*, **498**, 6083
 Eilers A.-C., Davies F. B., Hennawi J. F., 2018, *ApJ*, **864**, 53
 Fan X., et al., 2003, *The Astronomical Journal*, **125**, 1649–1659
 Fan X., Carilli C. L., Keating B., 2006a, *ARA&A*, **44**, 415
 Fan X., et al., 2006b, *AJ*, **132**, 117
 Gaikwad P., et al., 2020, *MNRAS*, **494**, 5091
 Gaikwad P., Srianand R., Haehnelt M. G., Choudhury T. R., 2021, *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society*, **506**, 4389–4412
 Garaldi E., 2023, *The Journal of Open Source Software*, **8**, 5407
 Garaldi E., Compostella M., Porciani C., 2019, *MNRAS*, **483**, 5301
 Garzilli A., Bolton J. S., Kim T.-S., Leach S., Viel M., 2012, *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society*, **424**, 1723–1736
 Giallongo E., et al., 2015, *A&A*, **578**, A83
 Giallongo E., et al., 2019, *ApJ*, **884**, 19
 Glatzle M., Ciardi B., Graziani L., 2019, *MNRAS*, **482**, 321
 Glatzle M., Graziani L., Ciardi B., 2022, *MNRAS*, **510**, 1068

- Glikman E., Djorgovski S. G., Stern D., Dey A., Jannuzi B. T., Lee K.-S., 2011, *The Astrophysical Journal*, 728, L26
- Graziani L., Maselli A., Ciardi B., 2013, *MNRAS*, 431, 722
- Graziani L., Ciardi B., Glatzle M., 2018, *MNRAS*, 479, 4320
- Greig B., Mesinger A., Haiman Z., Simcoe R. A., 2017, *MNRAS*, 466, 4239
- Greig B., Mesinger A., Bañados E., 2019, *MNRAS*, 484, 5094
- Gunn J. E., Peterson B. A., 1965, *ApJ*, 142, 1633
- Hariharan N., Graziani L., Ciardi B., Miniati F., Bungartz H. J., 2017, *MNRAS*, 467, 2458
- Hiss H., Walther M., Hennawi J. F., Oñorbe J., O’Meara J. M., Rorai A., Lukić Z., 2018, *The Astrophysical Journal*, 865, 42
- Hoag A., et al., 2019, *ApJ*, 878, 12
- Hockney R. W., Eastwood J. W., 1988, *Computer simulation using particles*
- Hunter J. D., 2007, *Computing in Science and Engineering*, 9, 90
- Jones E., Oliphant T., Peterson P., 2001
- Kannan R., Garaldi E., Smith A., Pakmor R., Springel V., Vogelsberger M., Hernquist L., 2021, *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society*, 511, 4005
- Komatsu E., et al., 2011, *ApJS*, 192, 18
- Lidz A., Faucher-Giguère C.-A., Dall’Aglio A., McQuinn M., Fechner C., Zaldarriaga M., Hernquist L., Dutta S., 2010, *The Astrophysical Journal*, 718, 199–230
- Loeb A., Barkana R., 2001, *Annual Review of Astronomy and Astrophysics*, 39, 19
- Ma Q.-B., Fiaschi S., Ciardi B., Busch P., Eide M. B., 2022, *MNRAS*, 513, 1513
- Madau P., 2017, *The Astrophysical Journal*, 851, 50
- Maselli A., Ferrara A., Ciardi B., 2003, *MNRAS*, 345, 379
- Maselli A., Ciardi B., Kanekar A., 2009, *MNRAS*, 393, 171
- Mason C. A., Treu T., Dijkstra M., Mesinger A., Trenti M., Pentericci L., de Barros S., Vanzella E., 2018, *The Astrophysical Journal*, 856, 2
- Matthee J., et al., 2022, *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society*
- McGreer I. D., Mesinger A., D’Odorico V., 2015, *MNRAS*, 447, 499
- McGreer I. D., Fan X., Jiang L., Cai Z., 2018, *AJ*, 155, 131
- Monaghan J. J., 1992, *ARA&A*, 30, 543
- Naidu R. P., Tacchella S., Mason C. A., Bose S., Oesch P. A., Conroy C., 2020, *The Astrophysical Journal*, 892, 109
- Naidu R. P., et al., 2021, *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society*, 510, 4582
- Nakane M., et al., 2024, *ApJ*, 967, 28
- Parsa S., Dunlop J. S., McLure R. J., 2018, *MNRAS*, 474, 2904
- Pentericci L., et al., 2014, *The Astrophysical Journal*, 793, 113
- Planck Collaboration et al., 2014, *A&A*, 571, A16
- Raskutti S., Bolton J. S., Wyithe J. S. B., Becker G. D., 2012, *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society*, 421, 1969
- Robertson B. E., Ellis R. S., Furlanetto S. R., Dunlop J. S., 2015, *ApJ*, 802, L19
- Rorai A., Carswell R. F., Haehnelt M. G., Becker G. D., Bolton J. S., Murphy M. T., 2017, *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society*, 474, 2871–2883
- Schaye J., Theuns T., Rauch M., Efstathiou G., Sargent W. L. W., 2000, *MNRAS*, 318, 817
- Spina B., Bosman S. E. I., Davies F. B., Gaikwad P., Zhu Y., 2024, *A&A*, 688, L26
- Springel V., 2005, *MNRAS*, 364, 1105
- Springel V., Yoshida N., White S. D. M., 2001, *New Astron.*, 6, 79
- Tepper-García T., 2006, *MNRAS*, 369, 2025
- Tilvi V., et al., 2014, *The Astrophysical Journal*, 794, 5
- Trebitsch M., et al., 2021, *Astronomy & Astrophysics*, 653, A154
- Umeda H., Ouchi M., Nakajima K., Harikane Y., Ono Y., Xu Y., Isobe Y., Zhang Y., 2024, *ApJ*, 971, 124
- Viel M., Haehnelt M. G., Springel V., 2004, *MNRAS*, 354, 684
- Viel M., Schaye J., Booth C. M., 2013, *MNRAS*, 429, 1734
- Walther M., Oñorbe J., Hennawi J. F., Lukić Z., 2019, *The Astrophysical Journal*, 872, 13
- Weigel A. K., Schawinski K., Treister E., Urry C. M., Koss M., Trakhtenbrot B., 2015, *MNRAS*, 448, 3167
- Wood K., Loeb A., 2000, *ApJ*, 545, 86
- Yang J., et al., 2020, *ApJ*, 904, 26
- Zhu Y., et al., 2024, *MNRAS*, 533, L49
- Žurovčíková D., et al., 2024, *ApJ*, 969, 162
- van der Walt S., Colbert S. C., Varoquaux G., 2011, *Computing in Science and Engineering*, 13, 22

APPENDIX A: SOME EXTRA MATERIAL

Here we’ll write about some additional materials.

This paper has been typeset from a $\text{\TeX}/\text{\LaTeX}$ file prepared by the author.